

(Re)Claiming African Agency: Analysis of the Enduring Impact of (Neo)Colonialism in Africa

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Abstract

This study seeks to identify avenues that Africa can utilise to navigate through the neocolonial and imperial ploys to (re)claim African agency. Local initiatives and willpower (agency) that speak to domestic emancipatory goals have, for too long, been ignored and hence robbed Africa of its authentic social and economic growth. Therefore, agency (i.e., the capacity to influence one's destiny) is an imperative if Africa is to grow sustainably. This study relied on a qualitative method of inquiry which leaned on document analysis. A qualitative method is best suited for the comprehensive examination of non-quantifiable phenomena such as the topic on African agency and neocolonialism. Thus, a qualitative route is effective in allowing for a critical evaluation of the foundational and functional aspects of phenomenon that are not easy to quantify. Data were collected through a synthesis of primary and secondary materials through scholarly journals, books and online publications.

The study finds that the problem of neocolonialism is twofold; as such, the blame does not rest solely on the doorsteps of imperial powers. For instance, while imperialists have demonstrated an appetite of resource extraction in Africa at any cost, there are also deep internal weaknesses within the African governance system that have made it possible for neocolonial traits to thrive.

The study notes that with prudent resource utilisation and fiscal discipline, Africa, like the 'Asian Tigers', can also grow incrementally and sustainably. Crucially, educational policies, i.e., the reforming of general education curricula and pedagogy coupled with innovative vocational training must be at the centre of developmental analysis. Aligning educational systems with local labour market demands is going to be an essential component of the national investment portfolio. The novelty of this study is that it addresses a topical issue of neocolonialism, thus, positions the conversation at the forefront of a decolonial discourse. It moves away from seeing Africa from a victim-hood mindset, and instead focuses on a perspective of adaptive resilient frameworks rooted in postcolonial emancipatory paths that aim to curtail imperial injustices. Thus, instead of merely being descriptive, the study is also prescriptive – aligning with the activist causes rooted in human rights dialogues. In this way, the study proactively contributes to the synthesis of critiques of neocolonial systems that have stagnated African agency for far too long.

Keywords: *African agency, Neocolonialism, Emancipation, Sustainable development, Human rights.*

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Introduction

This study is motivated by questions of how Africa can attain agency and growth for its population and how locals can become the legitimate agenda setters of their destiny to free themselves from neocolonial ploys. The research question for this study, therefore, is: how, and to what stretch does neocolonialism restrain African agency on development agendas?

While colonialism is largely considered as a past event, neocolonial agendas have emerged in various concealed forms. These forms include, among others, linguistic imperialism, control of international financial systems, imbalanced trade and engineering commodity prices (Vorozhbyt & Shaipova, 2025). Despite flag independence in Africa, the domination of global commerce by the West has systematically lowered subaltern agency. Aid, purportedly marketed as a means to alleviate poverty has caused more harm than good as it is merely used as a neocolonial instrument of domination (Fentahun, 2023). As Moyo (2009) has argued, aid has only served to increase poverty and thus, has made Africans more poorer than they were before. In many instances, aid is exploited as a trade-off for sovereignty. The subtle, but rent-seeking nature of neocolonial agendas makes neocolonialism a more advanced and perilous form of colonial oppression towards the subaltern populations (Nkrumah, 1965).

Saadawi (1994) asserts that the most menacing colonial shackles are the invisible ones (neocolonial tactics), because they deceive people into believing they are free. This delusion is the new prison that people inhabit today. The greatest illusion of power is to make the oppressed believe they are free. Colonisers see the colonised as inferior and less intelligent people whose agency is weak and thus, can have their natural resources exploited willy-nilly by external forces. Neocolonialism is understood as a covert enforced system of methodical subjugation of others, especially along racial lines by controlling local people and their territory mainly for resource extraction (Ake, 1981; Kohn & Kavita, 2024). Nkrumah (1965) describes neocolonialism as the last stage of imperialism.

Agency is the capacity to think and direct one's life autonomously. Such agency can be exercised by a collective or individually (Sustainability Directory, 2024). In agency, there is a significant component of freedom and intentional action to actively take initiatives to achieve specific goals. Agency involves the broad capacity to influence one's functionings (Bandura, 2023). Through cognitive self regulation, humans can envision their future and act on it through evaluation and modification of current trends. In all these processes, agents must be active because actions are part of the natural order (Mayr, 2012). Welzel & Inglehart, (2010) assert that feelings of agency are linked to human well-being through a sequence of adaptive mechanisms that promote human development in the face of existential conditions.

Thus, a developmental ideal for Africa requires fostering diverse ideas and agencies of inclusive and adaptive governance in line with the African Renaissance project. The Renaissance is an acknowledgement of past failures, and thus, calls for a rebirth to self-determination. It is a project that sees genuine growth through home-grown ideas, and that Africa cannot attain its full potential without the liberation of all marginalised groups (Daudu & Asuelime, 2019). Scholars such as Ngugi wa Thiong'o and Sabelo Ndlovu-Gatsheni see the Renaissance as project of *remembering* of a continent and a people who have suffered from *dismembering* effects of colonialism. The Renaissance therefore, is a renewed effort to proactively move away from the (neo)colonial dehumanisation and reduction of the African people to tradable commodities (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2019). In this study, the words, African/Black person will be used interchangeably, and similarly, the words, European/the West, will also be interchanged.

Due to intricate imperial power dynamics, indigenous African knowledge systems, i.e., African agency, has continued to be overlooked and stigmatised hence the need to focus on decolonial processes to reverse this imperial trend of dominance (Amuzu, 2024).

As such, it is necessary to find avenues that can utilise cultural sensitivity and reflexivity as a lever upon which decolonial discourses can be built to dismantle neocolonialism to reclaim African agency. An important question that an observer would ask is: to what extent have the states of Africa reclaimed their agency in light of the ongoing neocolonial practices that have made the African person anxious?

By imposing Western values in the global body politic, colonisers impede local agency that is necessary for sustainable growth (Fentahun, 2023). Consequently, an average African has become an anxious person who cannot seem to see the 'light at the end of the tunnel'. Lytovchenko et al. (2026) describe anxiety in contemporary society as something that increases people's vulnerability. They argue that:

... anxiety in contemporary society goes beyond a purely clinical or psychological phenomenon and becomes an integral characteristic of human existence under conditions of instability. Social acceleration, crises, information overload, and fragmentation of life trajectories contribute to the formation of anxiety as a constant background of everyday life. It is demonstrated that anxiety is associated with a transformation in the mode of being-in-the-world, manifested in the loss of predictability, weakening of long-term meaning orientations, and an increase in existential vulnerability (Lytovchenko et al., 2026, p. 1).

The absence of subaltern agency in international relations has also led to an increase in bigotry. Today, there are emerging concerns about what looks like a global rise in hatred being directed at members of certain ethnic, religious, and racial groups, including foreigners and other minorities. Ironically, what used to be considered as extremist ideas have now come to the political mainstream, accompanied by a nativistic and intolerant frame. This bigoted view also attacks efforts that would maintain multilateral consensus to nurture social justice (UN Human Rights Commission, 2019).

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative methodological framework, leaning on document analysis which is best suited for rigorous examination of complex, non-quantifiable phenomena (Saldana, 2009). Qualitative research has a wide variety of approaches and methods for the study of social life. A qualitative perspective allows for a critical evaluation of the functional aspects such as in the case of this study, the issue of African agency and neocolonialism – themes that are not easy to quantify. Lim (2025) asserts that the value of qualitative research lies in its capacity to generate contextual insights that connects research to real-world phenomenon. In this study (which relied on document analysis), relevant data related to African agency and neocolonial practices were collected through a methodical synthesis of data. Bowen (2009) assert that document analysis is the systematic procedure for reviewing and interpreting documents to gain their meaning. Documents of all types may be used as sources to help develop the meanings of phenomenon. Atkinson & Coffey (2004) add that document analysis provides background and context of the available information. The method also works as a means of tracking change and development.

In this study, the information base included sources such as academic journal articles, scholarly books, and online publications. The analytical procedure took a generic inductive approach as proposed by Creswell (2009). This method began with organising and processing of raw data, which was then followed by a systematic examination using information segmentation or coding to discover and interrelate the emerging themes. The coding process was done manually. Berthet et al. (2023) points out that the value of coding is that it organizes dense data into manageable amounts and helps to make sense of it by revealing trends and patterns. Thus, coding and interpretation are necessarily intertwined. This entails being open to expecting various kinds of patterns that may emerge, requiring adjustments in the analysis of data. Thus, in this study, the

analysis was concluded by deriving meanings connected from various themes that provided broader insights on the findings. To confirm the findings' reliability, this study used triangulation, which involved cross-referencing material from different sources to synthesise a comprehensive view of crucial topics. Carter et al. (2014) posit that triangulation is useful because it allows for convergence of data from different sources, thereby aiding the validation of the findings.

However, the **limitations** of this study are as follows:

(1) The study relied on document analysis, thus, did not conduct any interviews to get a first-hand perspective of stake holder views on African agency such as views from government officials, views from the African Union (AU) officials, views from civil society organizations, standpoints from representatives of local and traditional authorities, as well as perspectives from ordinary citizens. As such, future studies may focus on exploring these research gaps.

(2) The study's reliance on a qualitative research path also means that it lacks the quantitative capacity that could enable it to meticulously measure the social, political and economic impact of neocolonialism. Further, neocolonialism as a theme is hard to define; for instance, the South-South cooperation mechanism which Africa favors, may itself have nuanced exploitative elements of neocolonialism. Also, due to the complex nature of agency as a concept, defining it appropriately to establish the extent to which the African leaders are exercising autonomy or not, may result in the analysis itself being subjective.

(3) Qualitative document analysis research has elements of bias in how the documents are selected and scrutinized. Šimundić (2013, p.12) observes that bias in research can occur either wittingly or unwittingly, but the net result is that it leads to false conclusions. Often, bias happens when a researcher consciously influences the research process where themes are shaped and directed by researcher preferences. As such, the first step to conducting a credible qualitative research is for the researcher to be self-aware of this challenge and how it can influence the results of the study. In scientific research, a key principle of information assessment rests on the realization that correlation should not necessarily be linked to causation because data often under-determines theory. Researchers can look at the same data but come up with different findings (Goertz & Mahoney, 2012).

Despite having elements of bias, Lincoln & Guba (1985) and Tomaszewski et al. (2020) still see value in qualitative document analysis approaches because they speak to the central value of interpretative paradigms. If conducted meticulously, qualitative research can provide researchers with answers to critical questions about people and society. Other scholars such as Peshkin (1988) and Barone (2000) also posit that rather than rubbish subjectivity, a subjective analysis can also have the positive capability to shape data. For Peshkin and Barone, the real criteria of assessing a credible research lies in the researcher's ability to provide meaningful findings for a given subject matter.

To forestall the problem of bias, this study used triangulation, i.e., the use of a variety of sources to ensure that the findings were reliable. Noble & Heale (2019) assert that triangulation is a research approach used to provide validity and credibility to the findings through cross-checking of themes from different research sources. For Noble and Heale, credibility in this context refers to how believable a study is, i.e., how accurately it reflects the situation on the ground.

The Myth of the 'Civilization Agenda' and the Need to Pushback on Colonial Education

Camouflaging Civilization as their reason for invading African lands, the colonialists invoked alien modes of governance and foreign cultural practices which includes the imposition of religion (Fentahun, 2023). Studies such as Tishkoff et al. (2009) and Nweke (2015) show that Civilization of human kind began in Africa, not in Europe as is often purported. These studies show that humans originated from Africa more than 200,000 years ago and then began to move to other regions. This position is supported by the fact that the earliest systems of writings began in Africa, for instance, the Ge'ez scripts of Ethiopia around the 1st Century CE and the Nsibidi writings of Nigeria around the 4th century. Early Civilization works in Africa are also shown by Boye & Hunwick (2008) through medieval construction works; for instance, the works in Timbuktu (ancient Mali).

The fallacies of European explorers have added a layer of misinformation about knowledge systems in subaltern regions. For instance, in Zambia, a British colonial explorer, David Livingstone using a Eurocentric colonial fallacy claimed around 1855 to have discovered the Mosi-oa-Tunya Falls (which in local language means, 'the smoke that thunders') which he renamed as 'Victoria Falls', a name taken after the colonial England ruler, Queen Victoria (Siyabona Africa, 2025). Caroline Nenguke, a seasoned communication and advocacy expert in Zambia wonders how a European could have discovered what the indigenous people already knew existed. Nenguke drives the point home by arguing that, in part, that:

...our history records that the people who lived around the Mosi-oa-Tunya were awed by the magnificence of the falls, they revered it as a religious shrine, a place of worship and as such a sacred place. Therefore to say Dr Livingstone is the one that discovered the Victoria Falls is an insult to my people, taking into consideration that the word 'discover' according to the dictionary means 'to be the first person to find or learn something previously not known'. My ancestors knew about and had seen the Mosi-oa-Tunya, it is the people from Dr Livingstone's country or region that didn't know and that only makes him the first among his people but not the first in the world and certainly not among my people (Nenguke, November 17, 2010).

It strains credulity how such a false narrative of African realities gained prominence in Western writings and media. To be sure, such biased analyses of historical events which apparently are popularised in Europe would not pass a first-year History student at any university worth its salt.

For instance, in the majority of Western films/movies, there seems to be a sustained and nuanced racist *culture* of depicting people of colour as 'unscrupulous people' or as people with inherent bad characters. These stereotype attitudes include the ingrained perceptions where beauty, intelligence and civilisation are persistently molded around whiteness (Moser, 2006). Sarah Tue-Fee, a graphic designer exposes this bias in films by arguing that:

...our contemporary beauty standards are profoundly affected by the images we see in Western popular culture, which frequently privilege Caucasian aesthetics over those of any other ethnicity. As a result, the message that Whiteness is the default standard of beauty is perpetuated and internalised by people of colour around the world (Tue-Fee, 2016).

In social science research, such Western inferencing of people of colour fall under the category of biased research. Šimundić (2013) posit that biased research takes the form of deviating from the truth in the collection, analysis and interpretation of information. Such practices lead to false findings, thereby misrepresenting the reality on the ground: thus, bias in research is both unethical and immoral. Zahle (2025) adds that bias in qualitative research usually involves practices by researchers that purposely ignore data that does not align with their preconceived conclusions on a given topic. For this reason, Zahle argues that qualitative research may not, after all, contain much

quality especially because it lacks effective debiasing methods. Jerke et al. (2025) point out that in recent times, the *marketization* of science through academic policies that privileges success criteria based on index impact factors has contributed to a breeding ground of biased research findings and publications.

The picture below captioned as Figure 1, shows the contradictions of European narratives about Africa.

Figure 1. A Satirical Picture of the Local People, the Toka Leya Ethnic Group in Zambia Carrying David Livingstone to Show Him the Victoria Falls so that He Can ‘Discover It’
Source: TRT Afrika, 2026

Figure 2. The Mosi-oa-Tunya Falls
Source: Shutterstock.com, 2003-2026

Similarly, in the Americas, a European explorer, Christopher Columbus, claimed around 1492 to have discovered America. Given that indigenous people were already living in America, how did Columbus discover what was already known by locals? The fact is that in both of the above examples, indigenous peoples had populated those areas long before any European set foot on those territories. Tom Head, a historian, argues that Columbus did not discover America and there is no good reason to pretend that he did. Instead, what Columbus did was only to set up trade routes to exploit indigenous peoples of those lands (Head, 2025). The problem of a Eurocentric mindset is that Europeans want to impose their will on others without any due regard to the aspirations of indigenous peoples.

Scholarship, in particular, should be a vehicle of critical engagement that contributes to knowledge development. Crucially, academia should be a voice for articulating a better understanding of global affairs, so that all voices are heard without purposefully ignoring some (Simuziya, 2025a).

Bell Hooks asserts that education must be transformational in the sense of creating critical minds that questions things and challenges the status quo. For Hooks (1994, p.8.) every person's contribution matters because those contributions are themselves resources that influences societal dynamics. Lawrence Mwelwa, an academician, adds that schooling systems that do not teach learners to develop critical minds that can demand accountability are no more than systems of domestication. For Mwelwa, the price of refusing to challenge the status quo is to be ruled by colonial-minded elites who prey on the ignorance of the population (Africa Press, March 17, 2025).

Ramifications of Foreign Religions

The role of religion in the colonial project – of nuanced psychological capture of the mind, or otherwise the brain-washing of the minds of locals – is often underestimated. Religion has led to an African mindset built on compliance without critical thinking, whereby the African values are subordinated over European values (Adichie, 2016). Over time, Africans have come to be socialized around this colonial framing. Tragically for Africans, civilization itself is only seen from the prism of American/European replicas without much reflective reasoning, and this is now the psychological burden that most Africans carry in their minds (Williams, 1992).

The psychological impact of colonialism and religion is that it has built a passive African person; an African who suffers from an inferiority complex. This complex has led to most Africans believing that anything 'African' is backward, and anything European represents 'progress'.

Trained in colonial style education, many African academicians have also fallen into this trap of blind loyalty to Western ideas where they are now the ones in the forefront aiding the coloniser in vilifying African initiatives (Nhemachena & Mawere, 2022). It has been observed that most Black scholars tend to lose their sense of self, identity, and intellectual curiosity just to be someone whom other people want them to be. Complacency supplemented by a victim-hood mindset seems to be a major stumbling block in the fight against domination and discrimination. The most common Black scholars' responses to downright discrimination include passive phrases such as: 'It's okay'; 'you have to choose your battles wisely'; 'you have to tone down'. These defeatist and timid responses have become the familiar *language* of Black cowards and potential sell-outs who act to dissuade brave Black scholars from pursuing justice. Cowards prefer to 'keep the peace' – to keep false peace – lest their White masters get upset (Malcolm X, 1963). This *laissez-faire* attitude of 'hoping for the best' or having the *leap of faith in human nature and societal rules crafted by elites* is the worst form of naivety, which shows a lack of thorough understanding of the reality of political life; for politics have no bond with morals. The lesson from Machiavelli (1921) is that in policy analysis, it must be presupposed that human beings are *wicked*, and they will always act according to the

wickedness of their spirits when opportunity strikes. As such, beneficiaries of the status quo policies (i.e., discriminatory systems) will never willingly give up their *appetite* to continue their hold on those policies unless they are stopped by force. History teaches us that assuming evil away often opens a window for evil to reign freely. The logic of this argument is that the human mind is governed by desire instead of reason, and as such, people often put their welfare/interests first even in situations where the benefits to them are so little and the cost to others, enormous (Machiavelli, 1921, pp. 69-75). Steve Biko, a legendary South African freedom fighter, implored Africans to courageously (re)awaken themselves by embracing the Black consciousness philosophy when he asserted that:

... the first step (to change the status quo) is to make the Black man to come to himself (to galvanize his agency); to pump back life into his empty shell; to infuse him with pride and dignity, to remind him of his complicity in the crime of allowing himself to be misused, and therefore, letting evil (discrimination and racism) reign supreme (Biko, 2022).

There seems to be a desperate desire by some Black scholars to transform themselves by suppressing their true selves just to fit the mold as a way of gaining validation from White authorities. In this way, their authenticity and individuality are lost due to such *positive illusions* – simulacrum akin to what Marx & Engels (1936 [1852]) described as false consciousness. This delusion is the new prison of most Black people’s minds. Invisible chains are the most menacing ones because they delude people into believing that they are free (Saadawi, 2009). Further, many Black people including scholars have been brainwashed with religious dogmas, such as in Christianity, where Jesus is still fallaciously portrayed as a White person. The Christian propaganda and myth of a White Jesus is so ingrained in their scripts that to date, an average African Christian cannot conceive of a Jesus who is not White. The history of Christian culpability in systematic racism and maligning African cultural and spiritual practices is well documented; Christianity is a theology steeped in entrenched whiteness, and the concept of a White Jesus is a powerful tool upon which White supremacy reigns (Jun et al., 2018).

Religions teach blind loyalty to the faithful without allowing for the application of critical reasoning. This problem is aptly captured by Angelito Malicse who argued that:

...blind obedience to religious authority justified unimaginable cruelty in the name of faith. Blind Obedience continues to manifest in various ways today. In Religion, religious extremism often arises from blind obedience. While religion can promote morality, blind obedience can be dangerous when it discourages critical thinking. In Social Media in the digital age, blind obedience appears in the form of misinformation and propaganda. Many people accept fake news, conspiracy theories, and political lies without fact-checking (Malicse, 2025).

Malicse (2025) points out that critical thinking skills are required to subvert dogmas and unlawful orders. For instance, officials who played a key role in organizing the Holocaust, later defended their deeds by arguing that were just ‘following instructions.’ But the Nuremberg Trials refused to accept this dogmatic reasoning, asserting that individuals are responsible for their deeds, even when acting under orders.

Zireva & Pitsoe (2025) notes that literalism in the interpretation of religious scripts often leads to pseudo-intellectualism – a notion rooted in historicism where the faithful declare that they know the will of God. Due to rigidity, religious dogmas have ended up fortifying discriminatory attitudes, including within their own groups – such as discrimination against women - where misogyny and other entrenched patriarchal-dominated mindsets and power structures suppress women’s possibilities, effectively turning women into *present absentees* (Jenkins, 2023). Keith Soko, an associate professor of moral theology at St. Ambrose University in Davenport, weighs in on the problem of blind obedience when he argued that:

...another issue not addressed in some people’s nostalgia for a 1950s model of church that focused on law and obedience is the pedophile scandal. While that version of church had a uniformity, serenity and authority,

we know now that it had a dark underbelly. While the church may be a divine institution, it is also a human institution. The pedophile scandal exposed elements of the church over a number of decades that were not only sinful, but illegal (The Catholic Messenger, April 29, 2009).

For instance, to date, there are hardly any women in key church positions such as Reverends/ Bishops, implicitly suggesting that women are not *capable* of holding higher positions in public service. This suggestion is a tale that is far from the truth because women (in traditional African society) have excelled in various public roles, such as being village head-women. To date, some of the revered traditional/spiritual doctors (known in local language as ‘Sangomas’) are women. Unlike in religion, the African pre-colonial spiritual way of life never categorized women as being ‘less than men’, but as equal society members playing complementary roles (Mboh & Ekobi, 2022; Day, 2021).

It also seems bizarre that the colonial church, which has existed in Africa for about 600 years, has not yet identified any *capable women* to fill some of its key leadership positions. This narration shows how disconnected the religious systems are from practical life. This disjuncture (from reality) is the reason why most Biblical scripts are often interpreted out of context, with narratives exploited for self-serving and manipulative ends (Jenkins, 2023). Unsurprisingly, the Western church *endorsed* slavery and colonialism and hence was able to drive a subtle but vigorous ulterior agenda to subjugate Africans. It must be common knowledge, then, that the church could not and cannot (in its current configuration) genuinely fight for the human rights of the very people it set out to marginalize, exploit, and humiliate. The fallacies of the church have continued to date, and few Black scholars dare to publicly slam those dogmas, for they (the Black scholars) are beneficiaries, hence traitors of their people. Thus, as beneficiaries of imperial exploits such as Christianity, maintaining the status quo through complacency is very much in their interest (Ogun, 2021).

Such types of Africans, i.e., *the coconuts* (brown outside but white inside), are those whom Malcolm X referred to as ‘house negros’, meaning Africans who are willing to do the bidding of the colonizer, including bids that will cost their African authenticity. These are the types that avoid anything that looks like a revolution; they are *intellectually constipated* people, often hiding behind laptops. We live in the age of technology of false consciousness – the technology of concealing truths behind affable humanitarian clichés (Malcolm X, 1963).

From the slavery days, discrimination has been *justified* by literature by White historians who presented Black people as second-class citizens (King, 2014, p.2). Further, a *flood* of media propaganda infused with yellow journalism has also been a significantly destabilizing factor that has perpetually sustained negative narratives about Africa. Woodson (1933, p.3) and Turner et al. (1984) assert that historical and social studies books by most White authors inferred that Black people were cursed and barbarians with questionable intellectual acumen. Africans are stereotyped as dependent people who need alms for a lifeline and who are simply a European burden. Often, lighter skin is associated with beauty, intelligence, and wealth, while darker skin is stigmatized and associated with poverty and lower social status. These negative stereotypes are deeply embedded in the average European’s psyche.

The Challenge of Linguistic Colonialism

From the prism of the colonizer, an African person needs European guidance for them to lead a ‘normal and civilized’ life, hence the necessity to impose European values upon them. The ideological colonialism of imposing values on others without due regard to local cultural and historical contexts is the hallmark of colonial indoctrination which is championed through language control (Simuziya, 2025a).

Razmjoo & Barani (2025) argue that language is never a neutral process as it affects identity formation and shape the social and economic structures. Bourdier (1991) adds that language is not merely a model of communication but also a power mechanism. The language a person uses is designed by a person's relational position in a social space. As such, language determines who has the right to be heard and who can interrupt and play the role of 'leader'. Such representation manifests mainly through dialect and accent. Because of the power asymmetries associated with language, this leads to bias in how people are treated where those with high linguistic capital are given priority over others. Simuziya (2025a) argues that in Africa, colonial languages were imposed by the colonizers under the false pretense that those languages would play a neutral role given that there were several local languages. But language is never a neutral element because behind the veil, English, French and Portuguese worked to supplant local values with Western cultural values. Over time, local languages were stigmatized and seen to be inferior to foreign languages.

The power of language can be also be demonstrated in other jurisdictions. For instance, Kocherhin et al. (2026) points out that during the Soviet era, 'Russification policies' were implemented across the entire country under the banner of 'internationalism'. In this way, it is argued that because the Russian language was constitutionally made as the language of inter-ethnic communication, such a policy contributed to the marginalization of the Ukrainian language in the public sphere. Despite the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Russian language continued to operate as a critical avenue of cultural and informational influence. This was mainly done through the educational system, the media, and other key areas that influenced a shared information space, and thus, continued to subtly nurture the bygone soviet-era narratives. Woldeyes (2025) points out that in many African states, education focuses on teaching in European languages and foreign ideologies at the expense of indigenous languages and knowledge systems. Education in the language of former colonial powers was/is a tool of control rooted in the idea that Europeans are more knowledgeable, wiser and more competent than Africans.

Stagnation of Emancipatory Goals due to Imperial Wars Masked as Wars to Protect 'Human Rights'

Under the UN Charter (1945) rules, the international system need to reflect efforts towards peace and security. However, the reality on the ground suggest that powerful Western countries often ignore this requirement in pursuit of their hegemonic agendas (Musa et al. 2016). In Libya, for instance, the NATO forces invaded the country and deposed the Gaddafi regime in 2011 on the false pretense that they wanted to restore democracy and human rights in the country. Alas, NATO has failed to achieve that purported objective, and instead, has created a volatile state where competing militias have reduced Libya to a failed state. Libya has moved from one of the most economically stable countries in Africa to a lawless state where jungle law is the order of the day. Africa is still counting the cost arising from the 2011 NATO invasion (Simuziya, 2025a). Terry (2015) asserts that the way in which NATO implemented the UN Security Council resolution number 1973 on Libya, overstepped the limits of the said resolution; from protection of civilians to regime change. This was a violation of international law that governs warfare and humanitarian interventions in sovereign states. Ulfstein & Christiansen (2013) argue that by overstepping the limits of the resolution, NATO reduced the credence of future humanitarian interventions dubbed, 'responsibility to protect'. Indeed, many Global South states today have misgivings about Western claims of such interventions. Igwe (2013) points out that the real reason for the Libya intervention was to remove Gaddafi because he had progressive economic plans for Africa that could have potentially crippled Western financial and trade influence in Africa. For instance, among other proposals, Gaddafi was actively pursuing plans such as the establishment of a Pan-African currency

supported by gold along with the establishment of the African Investment Bank to be based in Libya.

The US-led unlawful invasion of Iraq in 2003 is another stark reminder that Western interventions under the guise of ‘human rights’ are – in the main – nothing more than colonial conquests to further Western foreign policies in subaltern states. The human rights atrocities committed by US and UK forces against Iraqi war prisoners brings into question the utility of human rights as a vehicle for transformation (Simuziya, 2023).

Recently in Australia, one of the most decorated former soldier has been charged with murdering unarmed war prisoners in Afghanistan. The back story is that a 2020 military probe revealed glaring allegations of gross misconduct among Australian forces who had been sent to Afghanistan to fight the Taliban regime between 2009 and 2012. The report reveals that troops were engaged in heinous war crimes such as summary executions of non-combatants including what the report calls ‘body count’ competitions (Sky News, April 7, 2026). Ironically, the troops were sent to Afghanistan to liberate the population from alleged human rights abuses by the Taliban regime. Thus, the conduct of troops is not simply at loggerheads with the claimed purpose of the troop deployment, but also justifies the Global South states’ misgivings on Western military interventions. In this context, Woldeyes (2025) brings out a deeper critique on the understanding of the meaning of human rights and their *complicity* in being part of the violence of the colonial nation-state. The main argument here is that human rights themselves often serve to camouflage the colonial violent functioning of a nation-state. The colonial effect is the resurgence of patterns of (neo)colonialism where imperial state structures keep reproducing the opposite of their stated democratic ideals.

There is a troubling trend, whereby Western powers seem to see every political problem that arise in subaltern countries as something that requires military intervention. Alas, military aggression – as contemporary history has shown – often destabilises the very social structures meant to protect human rights (Simuziya, 2021, p. 12). To gain public support, these military interventions, otherwise colonial wars, are dressed in rhetoric of ‘humanitarian assistance’ purportedly for the restoration of human rights in the affected countries (Simuziya, 2023). From the UN Charter (1945) rules, any humanitarian intervention that occurs without the approval of the UN or without the consent of the relevant state, damages the international legal framework that is necessary to main human rights. As de Coning (2020) has cautioned, for a peace process to be self-sustaining, resilient social institutions need to emerge from within. Thus, foreign interventions that lack local support often end up worsening the very situation they intended to remedy. It is not possible to resolve a conflict on behalf of the affected society from the outside, and this point is emphasised by de Coning when he argues that:

... too much external interference will undermine self-organization. From a complexity perspective, one can say that every time an external or controlling agent intervenes to solve a perceived problem or to bring the system back within prescribed parameters, they interrupt the internal feedback process and thus deny the local system from responding to its own stimuli. Social institutions develop more sophisticated or complex forms of self-organization through trial and error over generations (de Coning, 2020).

One might ask; what has these examples of Iraq and Australia got to do with African concerns on neocolonialism? The answer lies in what Martin Luther King proclaimed when he argued that, ‘injustice anywhere is a threat to justice anywhere’ (King Jr., 1963). The problems that arise from wars affect the weaker economies of Africa much more than they affect the European economies; for instance, conflicts in the Middle East create volatility in energy markets. Mahder. H. Serekberhan, a political analyst, argues that in the current US-Israeli aggression against Iran, the war has wider repercussions for Africa with the potential to trigger other conflicts in some hot-spots of the continent (Pambazuka News, March 6, 2026).

Historically, Global South states are connected due similar cultural traits and comparable historical experiences of imperial and colonial exploitation. In the main, their relations are forged around solidarity and push-back mechanisms against marauding Western powers. Through their shared sense of peripherality, Global South states appreciate their members' transformative and emancipatory goals (Bull & Banik, 2025). Vorozhbyt & Shaipova (2025) explains those shared experiences more aptly by arguing that:

...across much of the Global South, the legacies of colonialism remain an essential framework for understanding contemporary inequalities, political fragility and struggles for cultural and economic self-determination.

Hogan & Patrick (2024) posit that rather than conceiving the Global South as an obstreperous collection of states, it should instead be seen as guiding concept of re-imagining of a rights-based international order. Under such an order, respect for the sovereignty each state must necessarily be the basis of international cooperation.

Such a position also reflects renewed grievances against Western hegemonies and the need for those disempowered to band together. This understanding of the Global South as a class division created by colonial powers who accumulate capital through the exploitation of weaker states, aligns with the standpoints of critical theory scholars such as W. E. B. Du Bois and Antonio Gramsci. Both of these scholars see imperialism as the highest stage of capitalism where subaltern populations are reduced to expendable objects in economic relations. Exploitation is not limited to the economies, but also carried out through cultural imperialism (Gramsci, 2021; Du Bois, 1999).

From this perspective of understanding Global South states, the perpetual Western destabilization of member states through imperial wars masked as 'liberation wars' or wars intended to bring about 'human rights' to locals is seen as an assault on the ideals of all subaltern states. Another case in point also relates to the current US and Israeli conflict with Iran, where the US President, Donald Trump, threatened to 'wipe out Iran's civilization' if Iran failed to fulfill a deadline condition of opening an oil route through the Strait of Hormuz. It is iconoclastic and flabbergasting for the US, a country that often preaches human rights to African states, and a member of the UN Security Council, to threaten that the whole population of over 90 million Iranian civilians could bear the consequences of military decisions (The New York Times, April, 7, 2026). Such a brazen threat, if it were to be carried out, would be an act of modern-day genocide and an atrocious war crime. Such a war crime would demand the arrest of all those involved starting from the political leadership up to the army officers to be tried by the International Criminal Court (ICC). Under the Rome Statute which established the ICC, Article 33 specifically forbids military officers to engage in acts of war crimes under the guise of 'orders' from superiors (The Rome Statute, 1998). Similarly, under the Geneva Conventions (1949) of the laws of war, an army officer who carries out an illegal order from superiors such as to commit war crimes of any kind is himself/herself culpable of the offense. This is expressed explicitly in Articles, 27, 32, and 147, read together with Articles 18, 29 and 33 of the Geneva Conventions IV (1949). Significantly, the Nuremberg trials set a precedence on this matter (of acting on orders) by rejecting pleas from soldiers who participated in committing crimes against humanity on the argument that they were 'simply acting on orders from superiors' (Military Times, 2025). Similarly, you cannot commit genocide under the pretext of self-defense.

To emphasize, when international security is threatened, the countries that bear the worst brunt of the ensuing consequences such as surges in oil prices, are the developing nations. But beyond Africa, security experts such as Elizabeth Braw, observe that apart from disrupting trade, the current US-Israeli conflict with Iran has also exposed strains between the US and its strategic partners both in Europe and in the Middle East. Many of those partners do not see the US as a credible security partner given its unpredictable and unilateral approach to conflicts (Atlantic Council, 2026).

Why Neocolonialism Still Persist in Africa: Examining Internal African Fragility

Apart from external interference, internal African weaknesses have also contributed to the persistence of neocolonialist ploys mainly due to poor educational curricula and weaponized incompetence by the Africans themselves (Simuziya, 2025a). These weaknesses include the adoption of foreign ideologies in a *copy and paste fashion* just to fit the mold. For instance, it is ironic that the pomp, mantra and promotion of democracy for its own sake, has done more harm than good to the African person. Granted, democracy, in and of itself, can be a good model when applied diligently within a specific sociological context.

However, in Africa, the first problem why democracy has under-performed is because it was imposed from outside and implemented through a top-down matrix, which effectively rendered it as an elite project. Professor Okey Onyejekwe, the Executive Secretary at the African Center for Governance & Economic Management (ACGEM) argues that high levels of illiteracy, unemployment, and poverty suggest that Africa needs its own organic development model that can respond intimately to local needs. The compounding problem is that the global financial architecture is more of an obstruction than a solution for social inclusion (ACGEM) (2025). Attoe (2024) adds that the failure of democracy in Africa arises mainly from the absence of proper quality education which has significantly contributed to having a population that lacks the skills of making informed decisions. It is ironic that democracy – a concept that preaches free choice – was imposed on the African masses. The contradiction could not be starker. As Don Collins Ouma, a political activist, put it, ‘Africa’s democratic decline is not a failure of culture or capacity – it is the logical outcome of a system designed from the beginning to extract, not to liberate’ (Pambazuka News, April, 17, 2026).

Gavristova & Khokholkova (2026) point out that in a post-colonial African reality, a colonial mindset has created the problem of an identity crisis. Colonial behaviors and their effects expressed in the writings of scholars such as Du Bois, Leopold Senghor, Diop Cheikh, Edward Said, and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, expose various indications of a psychological capture of the minds of locals. The most noticeable trait is the inferiority complex, accompanied by the affinity by the colonised to copy the way of life of the colonizer, which psychologically, deprives the African person of their authenticity and agency.

As noted earlier, the foremost challenge starts with way the African person is educated, i.e., colonial education that does not align with local needs. This type of misaligned learning is what Woodson (1933) referred to as, ‘the mis-education of the Negro’. The learning system especially rote learning, and other colonial-era pedagogy systems of education which are currently used in African schools do not reflect the interests, talents, and cultural aspects of local students. Simply put, education that ignores learners’ backgrounds, such as cultural and traditional value systems and the natural aptitude of students, is not only deficient but also harmful to those learners (Hooks, 1994). Also, Africa’s local political elites have done more damage than providing solutions towards sovereignty by allowing themselves to be puppets and political bagmen of imperialists. In this way, the elites have become what Ngugi wa Thiong’o described as, ‘local petty bourgeoisie’ (Ngugi, 1986). A related and equally concerning matter is the issue of weaponized incompetence: in most instances, African authority figures – despite attaining high academic qualifications – choose to perform only the bear minimum so that the population does not expect much from them. In this way, a gap is created which outsiders, especially those who prey on such loopholes exploit.

The role of *uncle Thoms*, i.e., the local traitors, and puppet political elites who still worship at the alter of Western imperialism have done significant damage to African solidarity against neocolonialism. Ironically, local elites are keen to maintain the status quo, i.e., maintaining the

monopoly of colonial privileges and structures because they benefit from those imperial spoils. Malcolm X (1963) called such Black people as, *House Negroes*, meaning, people who have sold diamonds for rocks, or people who are ready to forgo their African authenticity in exchange for imperial privileges.

The trouble today with the African person is that he/she seems to be in a catch 22 situation: on the one hand, the African person is no longer ‘truly African’ because he/she has abandoned his/her African knowledge systems in preference for Western value systems. On the other hand, despite the African person’s affinity for Western culture, (i.e. *diving* in European cultures headlong), he/she will never be European no matter how Westernized he/she might be because the racist description of who can be ‘European’ or ‘Western’ is someone with white skin color (Simuziya, 2025b, p.996).

The aloofness of the African Union (AU) is also a troubling factor in the equation of attaining agency in Africa, for instance, the former President of South Africa, Thabo Mbeki, does not seem to have much optimism in the AU, citing administrative bureaucracy and inertia (Simuziya & Jalu, 2025, p.10). Similarly, the President of Zambia, Hakainde Hichilema is equally perturbed by the slow pace of reforms within the AU. For Hichilema, the AU has reduced itself to a mere talk show where too much time is spent on playing politics instead of focusing on economic revival plans of Africa. For instance, too many people are leaving the continent to Europe for perceived greener pastures because of poor economic leadership in their home countries (Make Africa Great, 2025). The weakness and lack of sound leadership of the AU can also be seen on how it has failed to resolve many of the civil conflicts in several African conflict hot spots (Simuziya, 2021).

Prospects of Attaining African Agency to End the Invisible Chains of Neocolonialism

Because the AU is largely ineffective in fostering pan-African unity as well as in delivering the much needed reforms, it is imperative that regional bodies and individual states take the initiative to pursue radical reforms to achieve African agency. Currently, there is not much hope due to a fragmented AU leadership, whereby the organization relies on foreign funding for survival, hence is already captured by imperialists (Abdisamad, 2024). The starting point to pan-African awakening is to prioritize decolonizing key areas such as elevating local languages to the status of official languages. Already, Mali has shown political will by demoting the French language in 2023 in preference for local languages (Language Magazine, 2023).

Other decolonizing examples are in Burkina Faso where, for instance, the judicial dress code of judges now reflects the social norms of the Burkina Faso population as opposed to the colonial French judicial robes previously worn in the country (Simuziya, 2025a). Abzianidze (2026) notes that Burkina Faso, under Thomas Sankara (1983-1987) made significant strides despite the short period of time he served in office. Sankara’s political will led to the fight against illiteracy, the empowerment of women and self-sufficiency in food security. In this way, Sankara set the country on a path towards modernization in an organic way that is rooted in African contexts. Oladipupo (2025) sees modernity as a product of cultural dynamism and growth that reflects local cultural heritages, the *Africanization of modernity*. As such, the quality/capability of leadership, i.e., having leaders that are assertive and pragmatic is key in driving such dynamism and growth. Simura (2026) gives an example of Naledi Pandor, the former Minister of Foreign Affairs in South Africa whose leadership – he argues - contributed to establishing an assertive foreign policy rooted in an emancipatory postcolonial frame. Also, the *Nyerere Doctrine* of 1961 (by Julius Nyerere) is still a useful concept for Africans and aligns with the aims of the African Renaissance project to pursue policies that speak to local realities. The *Nyerere Doctrine* argues that independent African states are

not bound by colonial and imperial inheritance agreements except if Africans themselves consent to them (Makonnen, 1984).

Other examples of decolonizing the economies are seen through efforts to limit the export of raw materials by countries such as Ghana, Zambia, Namibia, and Botswana. These countries are arguing that the export of raw/unprocessed natural resources, especially minerals, need to cease in the near future because such a step will mean that Africa will have automatically stopped 'exporting jobs' overseas, since the processing of natural resources will have been localised. These countries have also stepped-up their collaborative efforts by simplifying cross-border movements through visa waivers to ease mobilities, trade and commerce (Business Insider Africa, 2026; Global African Times, 2025).

Many of these steps will be symbolic in the interim, but will gradually gain momentum. No doubt, the journey will be long and costly, but it will nevertheless be a necessary venture to finally liberate Africa. Scholars such as Chitonge (2025) insist that for the continent to be truly sovereign as envisioned in the African Renaissance project and the AU Agenda 2063, it needs to be economically self-sufficient otherwise it will continue to be controlled by colonialists (African Union, 2015). The African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights (ACHPR)(1981) preamble, states, in part, that:

... African people must be conscious of their duty to achieve the total liberation of Africa, the people who are still struggling for their dignity and genuine independence, and undertaking to eliminate colonialism, neo-colonialism, apartheid, zionism and to dismantle aggressive foreign military bases and all forms of discrimination, particularly those based on race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion or political opinion.

On promoting quality education, a growing number of African countries are stepping up their efforts. For instance, in Zambia the government presented a bill in parliament (in early 2026) which sought to guarantee free education for all children entering public schools from primary school level to secondary level (Lusaka Times, April 8, 2026). That Bill has now been passed into law, making education a legal right: this marks a seminar shift of translating policy into law (Zambian Observer, May 7, 2026).

Further, Africa can use legally recognized international instruments and conventions to challenge the supremacist attitudes in global politics. Such binding legal mechanisms include the United Nations (UN) Charter rules (1945), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) (1948), International Covenant for Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (1966), and the International Covenant for Economic Social and Cultural Rights ICESCR (1966).

Sumkoski (2025) points out that Africa needs industrialization programs governed by sovereignty and centered on indigenous control of production systems. Until Africa adopts its organic development models, the continent will continue to reproduce colonial and unsustainable economic outcomes. Linklater (1998) points out that agency can be exerted to achieve a more inclusive world through already existing normative mechanisms in international relations. For instance, the UN human rights conventions such as the UDHR (1948) and bodies such as United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (1945) together with relevant international legal instruments provide frameworks where people see each other as equals. For Linklater, rather than wait for future changes, people can find hope in the realization that transformational agency (for the future they desire) already exists within current social and political structures. Also, based on structural historical analysis, the key lesson of history is that due to the delusion of omnipotence, every empire falls...Rome fell, the Mongol empire fell, the British empire fell, and any other current empire will fall. On why empires fall, Xueqin Jiang, a professor specialized in predictive history in geopolitics weighs in by arguing in part, that:

...empires fall not because they were defeated militarily but because they overextended, and thus could not sustain the cost of empire. Their internal contradictions, corruption, loss of purpose and hubris caught up with them (Jiang, March 9, 2026).

Africa's agency can also be enhanced by forging stronger South-South ties such as with the BRICS states (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) given the common historical aspirations of the struggles for social, economic, and political emancipation.

Conclusion

This study provides a radical intellectual pathway that can empower Africans to take charge of their destiny, hence reclaim their agency. As such, the study contributes to the development of political theory in decolonial perspectives. The study notes that political independence in Africa has failed to deliver due to persistent foreign intrusions through neocolonial traits that manifest in various nuanced ways. Colonialism, imperialism and neocolonialism takes many forms of power asymmetries that have impacted the cultural and traditional identities of the African people. They include Western domination and control of global financial, trade and investment systems, linguistic colonialism, debt traps through loans for infrastructure development, and aid programs. Neocolonialism also involves the fomenting of colonial wars masked as wars intended to bring about democracy and human rights.

Crucially, neocolonialism also persists due to the psychological capture of the African mind channeled mainly through linguistic imperialism. Another aspect of cognitive control has to do with foreign religions which preach obedience without critical thinking. The study also notes that part of the problem of Africa's stalled growth comes from within. Many African local elites are complicit in the eradication of neocolonialism because they benefit from those imperial structures. In this way, the African person (the influential African) has become a traitor of his/her own homeland. Ngugi wa Thiong'o described these African treacherous elites as 'petty local bourgeoisie'. As Oladipupo (2025) has argued, the consequences of colonization have left Africans with dogmatic acceptance of their cultures as inferior and unscientific compared to Western cultures. A critical review, however, shows that the Western notions that perceive African cultures as 'backward' are built mainly on exaggerated premises of Western civilization. Those notions are also built on supremacist mindsets, bigotry, racism, self-importance, and a lingering colonial mindset. Today, neocolonialism can be seen through ideologies such as democracy. Like colonialism and religion, democracy itself – being an imposed system from outside – has proved to be a conduit of neocolonialism as it has lamentably failed to deliver the 'promised' tangible sustainable economic and political results. As Don Collins Ouma has aptly argued, 'Africa was not given democracy – it was given a system designed to fail' (Pambazuka News, April, 17, 2026). In this way, African agency is constrained by external arm-twisting tactics and influences that persistently stigmatize local initiatives. Thus, the first step needed to reverse this trend is to decolonize the educational system, whereby quality education must be available to all citizens to enable them to make informed choices. Additionally, such education must be driven by curricular, language, and pedagogy that speak to local environments and cultural values. Furthermore, to become truly sovereign, African will need to proactively discard all potential colonial structures that still hold back its local innovations and ingenuity. Emphasizing on policies and programs that can increase Intra-Africa trade is one critical avenue through which African agency can be reclaimed. This also means that the industrial production processes and control of African natural resources must be driven and directed by locals themselves. The bottom-line is that to achieve sustainable development, growth programs must be spearheaded from within, not from outside.

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